

Anthropometric Assessment and its Association with Health Risk Factors in Overweight and Obese Schoolchildren

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To cite this article:

Marcela Rosas Nexticapa, Lauro Figueroa Valverde, María Virginia del Socorro Mateu Armand, Catalina Cervantes Ortega, Elizabeth Montano Tapia, Elodia García Cervera, Isela Santiago Roque, Crescencio Hernández Osorio and Yudeysi de Jesús López Espinoza. "Anthropometric Assessment and its Association with Health Risk Factors in Overweight and Obese Schoolchildren". *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. v. 4, n. 5, 2018, pp. 25-31.

Received: June 29, 2018; **Accepted:** July 25, 2018; **Published:** July 27, 2018.

Abstract

Overweight and obesity is the single major public health problem in Mexico, ranking first in the world with children ailing from this condition, the present study aims to anthropometrically evaluate schoolchildren between the ages of 10 and 12 and determinate some biochemical blood tests. In addition, to evaluate some anthropometrically parameters were used the percentiles from the CDC (Center for Disease Control and Prevention) grow charts system. The results showed 22 children with malnutrition, 74 being underweight, 248 having a healthy weight, 128 with overweight and 199 with obesity. Girls showed a body mass index (BMI) of 24.98 ± 0.43 and 24.28 ± 0.42 in boys. Measurement of waist circumference (WC) was 79.06 ± 1.76 for girls and 80.73 ± 1.39 for boys. This phenomenon was associated with high triglycerides levels (90-129 mg/dl) and high Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP) in girls, which could be risk factor for development to cardiovascular disease in adulthood.

Keywords: Public health in Mexico, Schoolchildren, Obesity, Anthropometric, Cholesterol, Glucose, HDL, LDL, VLDL, Body Mass Index, Triglycerides.

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1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are main cause of death in worldwide; these clinical pathologies can be conditioned by some factors such as overweight and obesity. In addition, these two factors are characterized by excessive accumulation of body fat as a result of a higher caloric intake compared to the energy expenditure of the individual [1-5]. Overweight and obesity have reached global epidemic proportions. More than one billion adults are overweight; of which at least 300 million are obese, which results in increased cardiovascular disease at an early age 10. While long ago overweight and obesity were considered problems of high-income countries, currently, both disorders are increasing in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in urban environments [6-9]. Recent studies claim that there is a two to three times higher risk of becoming overweight or obese in adulthood by identifying a consistent association in the rapid weight gain during the first two years of life, with obesity in childhood and adulthood [10, 11]. Body mass index (BMI) is an indirect indicator of adiposity in child and adolescent; for example, there are several data found in six countries such as Brazil, Great Britain, Hong Kong, the Netherlands, Singapore and the United States which showed that BMI for overweight of 25 kg/m² and 30 kg/m² for obesity in populations of 18 years [11, 12]. In addition, other study carried out in 2006, indicates that these results are very confusing; therefore, were proposed two new sets of growth patterns for to evaluate the BMI on infants and children [13].

On the other hand, a study shown that in Mexico (Veracruz State) the prevalence of overweight and obesity in children between 5 and 11 years of age was 24.3% and 12.5%, respectively, ranking first nationally with overweight and obesity [14]. Analyzing, these epidemiological data, the aim of this study was to evaluate some anthropometrically parameters such as BMI, waist circumference, blood pressure, triglycerides and cholesterol to determinate overweight and obesity degree in schoolchildren between 10 and 12 years ago of Xalapa, Veracruz, Mexico.

2. Methods

Initially, it was negotiated with the Ministry of Education the authorization of the study in primary schools; subsequently, a process of

information and awareness towards teachers, parents and schoolchildren was conducted. Consent signed by parents or guardians was requested. The measurements were performed directly in a specific area at each school. The anthropometric assessment was performed by previously standardized nutritionists, subject to the specifications of the NOM-031-SSA2-1999 [15] for the health care of children and the CDC [16] references. The blood samples for biochemical tests were performed by clinical pharmacologists and clinical chemists that used the "glucose oxidase" method to determine glucose levels quantified by colorimetry, using the X Jr. Kitlab spectrophotometer at a 500 nanometers (nm) wavelength. For the determination of triglyceride, cholesterol, HDL, LDL and VLDL, a Teco Diagnostics (TC) kit was used and a 520 nm absorbance was measured in the X Jr. Kitlab spectrophotometer.

2.1. Subjects

In the present study, 671 fifth and sixth graded schoolchildren from elementary schools in the city of Xalapa, Veracruz with ages ranging from 10 to 12 years of age were anthropometrically evaluated.

2.2. Inclusion Criteria

Ten to twelve years aged male and female overweight and obese schoolchildren whose parents authorized their participation in the study.

2.3. Anthropometric Assessment

In order to obtain Body Weight (BW) measurements, Tanita pediatric scales [17] were used, the measuring unit was kilograms (kg) through the magnetic bioimpedance electronic system. Children were weighted without shoes and socks, with light clothing and before breakfast. The Height and/or size (S), was measured with a Seca fixed stadiometer. Waist circumference (WC) was measured in cm, with a Seca anthropometric tape, with the subject standing, feet slightly apart, and abdomen relaxed, a horizontal measure was taken at the narrowest point of the torso above the umbilicus and below the ribcage. The Body Mass Index (BMI) was obtained with the following equation: [BMI] =

[Kg/m²], relates weight and height square, equation:

$$BMI = \frac{Mass}{(Height)^2} \quad (1)$$

The diagnosis for overweight or obesity in schoolchild was determined by BMI in relation to gender, age with completed years and months, and Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) tables, which are used in populations aged 2-20 years. Overweight was diagnosed from the 85th and obesity from the 95th percentile, according to the CDC tables.

Table 1. Guidelines for interpreting total cholesterol values (TC), LDL, HDL, triglycerides in children and adolescents aged 2-19 years old.

Category	Level (mg/dl)	
Total Cholesterol		
High	200 or above	
High borderline	170 to 199	
Desirable	170 or Lower	
LDL Cholesterol		
High	130 or above	
High borderline	110 to 129	
Desirable	Less than 110	
HDL Cholesterol	10 years or <	10 to 19 years
Low	Below 40	Below 35
Low borderline	40 to 45	35 to 45
Desirable	45 or above	45 or above
Total Triglycerides		
High	100 or above	130 or above
High borderline	75 to 99	90 to 129
Desirable	Below 75	Below 90

Source: Peter M. Kwiterovich Jr. 1998. [2]

2.4. Biochemical Test

For biochemical tests, blood samples (4 ml) were taken in 6 ml BD Vacutainer Serum 368,175 tubes, without anticoagulant. Schoolchildren were presented fasting for between 8 and 12 hours, without any drug treatment. The lipid profile results performed to schoolchildren were compared with The Johns Hopkins, The Complete Guide for Avoiding Heart Disease reference values (1998) [2], (Table 1).

3. Statistical Analysis

The results were statistically analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 22.0) software; data is reported with mean and statistical error.

4. Results

Of a total of 671 schoolchildren anthropometrically assessed with the CDC percentile tables, 22 were diagnosed as malnourished, 74 with low weight, 248 with healthy weight, 128 overweight and 199 obese. Out of these students, only 124 entered the study with diagnoses of overweight or obesity, 62 boys and 62 girls with signed parental consent.

In the anthropometric assessment of 124 schoolchildren with overweight and obesity, girls had a weight of 56.58 ± 1.34 and boys a weight of 52.57 ± 1.30 ; girls had a height of 1.49 ± 0.17 and boys a height of 1.46 ± 0.98 . Girls had a BMI of 24.98 ± 0.043 and boys a 24.28 ± 0.42 BMI; waist circumference was found in girls with a mean of 79.06 ± 1.76 and 80.73 ± 1.39 in boys, (Table 2).

Table 2. Anthropometric characteristics of schoolchildren with overweight and obesity.

Characteristics	Girls(n = 62)	Boys(n = 62)
Age (years)	11.09 ± 0.08	11.16 ± 0.10
Weight (kg)	56.58 ± 1.34	52.57 ± 1.30
Size (cm)	1.49 ± 0.17	1.46 ± 0.98
Body Mass Index*	24.98 ± 0.43	24.28 ± 0.42
Waist circ.**	79.06 ± 1.76	80.73 ± 1.39

*BMI (kg/m²); **Waist circumference (cm).

Table 3. Biochemical Tests of overweight and obese schoolchildren.

Biochemical tests (mg/dl)	Girls (n = 62)	Boys (n = 62)
Glucose (GLU)	81.52 ± 1.39	83.37 ± 1.41
Cholesterol (TC)	140.05 ± 4.80	154.38 ± 5.05
HDL Cholesterol (HDL-C)	42.84 ± 3.21	38.42 ± 2.31
LDL Cholesterol (LDL-C)	86.39 ± 4.10	78.96 ± 4.43
VLDL Cholesterol (VLDL-C)	22.11 ± 1.56	20.41 ± 1.24
Triglycerides (TG)	107.74 ± 7.40	103.07 ± 6.12
Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP*)	0.396 ± 0.06	0.425 ± 0.05

*AIP = [Log (Triglycerides/HDL-Cholesterol)], Equation (2). [18]

$$AIP = \log \left(\frac{(TG)}{(HDL-C)} \right) \quad (2)$$

Table 4. Pearson Correlation (PC) analysis between biochemical tests

		GLU	CHOL	HDL	LDL	VLDL	TG	AIP*
GLU	PC	1.0000	0.0858	-0.0320	0.0869	0.0419	0.0273	0.1156
	Sig. Bi.	-	0.3436	0.7245	0.3375	0.6442	0.7633	0.2011
TC	PC	0.0858	1.0000	-0.1566	0.0877	0.2388	0.2582	-0.0336
	Sig. Bi.	0.3436	-	0.0823	0.3330	0.0076	0.0038	0.7111
HDL	PC	-0.0320	-0.1566	1.0000	0.1920	-0.0853	-0.0956	-0.0690
	Sig. Bi.	0.7245	0.0823	-	0.0326	0.3461	0.2907	0.4463
LDL	PC	0.0869	0.0877	0.1920	1.0000	0.0920	0.0899	0.0000
	Sig. Bi.	0.3375	0.3330	0.0326	-	0.3097	0.3208	0.9997
VLDL	PC	0.0419	0.2388	-0.0853	0.0920	1.0000	0.9630	0.0980
	Sig. Bi.	0.6442	0.0076	0.3461	0.3097	-	0.0000	0.0000
TG	PC	0.0273	0.2582	-0.0956	0.0899	0.9630	1.0000	-
	Sig. Bi.	0.7633	0.0038	0.2907	0.3208	0.0000	-	0.2635
AIP*	PC	0.1156	-0.0336	-0.0690	0.0000	0.0980	0.1012	1.0000
	Sig. Bi.	0.2011	0.7111	0.4463	0.9997	0.2787	0.2635	-

1. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (bilateral); glucose (GLU); total cholesterol (TC); triglycerides (TG); high density lipoprotein (HDL); low density protein (LDL); very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) *Atherogenic Index of Plasma (AIP); Pearson Correlation (PC); Sig (Bilateral) = Sig. Bi.

The biochemical tests results indicate, 81.52 ± 1.39 fasting glucose values for girls and 83.37 ± 1.41 for boys; TC results for girls were 140.05 ± 4.80 , compared with boys who obtained a mean of 154.38 ± 5.05 ; girls had an average HDL-C value of 42.84 ± 3.21 and boys an average value of 38.42 ± 2.31 , values below the desirable limits; The LDL-C values found in girls were of 86.39 ± 4.10 and an average value in boys of 78.96 ± 4.43 , the VLDL-C had an average value of 22.11 ± 1.56 in girls and in boys a value of 20.4 ± 1.24 ; triglycerides showed an average value in girls of 107.74 ± 7.40 and 103.07 ± 6.12 in boys, concentrations exceeding those indicated in The Complete Guide for Avoiding Heart Disease [1, 2], (Table 3).

When Pearson correlation analysis between biochemical tests were made, and value of 0.963 was found between the values of triglycerides and VLDL, which possibly predisposes schoolchildren in a later adulthood phase with atherogenic (AIP) [18] and thrombogenic problems, (Table 4).

5. Discussions

When performing the nutritional diagnosis of the students who participated in this study, of the 671 evaluated schoolchildren, 327 were diagnosed with overweight and obesity, representing 48% of the study population, and out of this population, only 18% ($n = 124$) schoolchildren agreed to participate in the biochemical tests, probably due to the tutor's lack of commitment to the health of their children. In our country, in recent years, psychological abuse and bullying among children has been growing, in most cases caused by the physical appearance of children, which causes negative effects on the children's emotional and social areas [19]. Therefore, the presence of overweight or obesity should be taken with responsibility in order to prevent damage caused by body perception, which could take an impact on the health of schoolchildren.

The anthropometric assessment of the $n = 124$ schoolchildren showed BMI values above the 85 and 95 percentiles, according to the CDC diagnostic tables. Regarding WC, it was found above the 75 percentile, diagnosed with reference values corresponding to the Mexican-American population reported [20]. The increase in WC in children and adolescents is associated with systolic and diastolic hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, low HDL cholesterol,

hypertriglyceridemia, insulin resistance and increased cardiovascular risk [21]. Other studies have also shown correlations with BMI and WC values, with high biochemical figures associated with overweight and obesity [22]. The WC in adults is a good indicator of abdominal mass directly related to the risk of cardiovascular disease] so it is important to be diagnosed in early ages to prevent future health complications due to the fact that it has been shown recently that children, similar to that found in adults, with central adiposity develop cardiovascular risk more frequently [23, 24, 25, 26].

By comparing the children's lipid profile results in this study, with values from The Johns Hopking The Complete Guide for Avoiding Heart Disease, HDL-C was found with values of 42.84 ± 3.21 and 38.42 ± 2.31 , respectively, being found within the low borderline values (35-45 mg/dl); children had triglyceride levels of 107.74 ± 7.40 and 103.07 ± 6.12 , being in the high borderline values (90-129 mg/dl). These results were compared with some studies carried out in child and adolescent athletes who showed average values of 172.57 ± 27.79 for TC, 56.01 ± 1.01 for HDL-C, 94.61 ± 24.26 for LDL-C and 56.23 ± 18.69 for TG [27]. Therefore, these data indicate that there are differences in the lipid profile [28], perhaps this phenomenon could be due to differences in the study populations.

Most dyslipidemia in children is primary. The most common primary dyslipidemia with increased LDL-C are familial hypercholesterolemia and familial combined dyslipidemia. It is estimated that one in 25 children with LDL-cholesterol above 130 mg/dl has a heterozygous familial hypercholesterolemia; homozygous is much less common. In familial hypercholesterolemia, elevated cholesterol figures are detectable at birth. In the homozygous form, cutaneous xanthomas may occur in the first months of life. The heterozygous kind has a frequency of about 1/500 or less and is more difficult to show early clinical manifestations. Familial combined dyslipidemia, is three times more common and may not manifest since childhood. It must be remembered that an inherited form of dyslipidemia is hypoalphalipoproteinemia² (HA) [29, 30], with

² Hypoalphalipoproteinemia is a high-density lipoprotein deficiency, inherited in an autosomal dominant manner. [29] It can be associated with LDL receptor [30].

less than 35 mg/dl of HDL cholesterol results of a routine lipid profile measurement. This finding of a low high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol level can be useful as an independent factor in assessing coronary artery disease (CAD) risk and further management [31, 32].

On the other hand, it is noteworthy that some reports indicate that exist a correlation between lipid profile and atherogenic index of plasma (AIP) [27]. In this sense, AIP was evaluated in the population of study; the results showed that there were no significant differences in the values of AIP between boys and girls. However, the values of HDL-C for the boys is low which could be a risk factor to development cardiovascular diseases; this premise is similar to other studies which indicate that HDL-C levels are a specific factor in assessing coronary artery disease risk [31, 32, 33].

6. Conclusions

Obesity, unlike other diseases, such as infections, cancer and mental illness, is a progressive disease that can be reversed or controlled more easily in its initial phase. Early detection of children with overweight and obesity can intervene and improve their quality of life, this with the participation and commitment of tutors and health professionals. This study intends to continue with the intervention in subjects with dietary guidance and the dosage of food supplements that improve blood lipid conditions.

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